

Research

A descriptive study on stroke in provincial hospital Janakpur, Nepal

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Abstract: Sub-Asian countries lack basic stroke data, and Nepal has none. To describe Janakpur provincial hospital stroke admissions epidemiologic description, patients with confirmed stroke from 1 July to 30 November 2019 had risk factor assessments. 127 stroke patients got a non-contrast head CT scan; 12 died before the scan. 85 patients suffered stroke, 42 had non-stroke lesions. 77.6% of stroke victims had ischemic stroke, while 22.4% had hemorrhagic. All stroke patients were 62.2 and 51.8% were men. Ischemic and hemorrhagic stroke increased with age. Atherosclerotic stroke was the most prevalent ischemic stroke etiology, seen in 43.5% of patients, and intraparenchymal hemorrhage was the most common hemorrhagic stroke etiology, seen in 78.9% of patients. More than 50% of stroke patients reported a history of hypertension, and more than half had blood pressure over 140/90 mm Hg. 36% and 30% of ischemic and hemorrhagic stroke patients had inactivity and hypercholesterolemia. Hypertension was the greatest risk factor for ischemic and hemorrhagic strokes. This study highlights the importance of CT scan in stroke diagnosis in Nepalese population.

Keywords: stroke, Nepal

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Introduction

The importance that patients have on the quality of the care they get has made patient feedback an integral aspect of the quality assessment process in hospitals. [1,2] Beginning in the late 1980s and continuing into the early 1990s, hospitals began investigating the possibility of developing outcome-based quality measures. Their primary focus was on "hospitality" indicators that were comparable to those utilized by hotels. [3,4] However, the publication of *Through the Patient's Eyes: Understanding and Promoting Patient-Centered Care* [5] in 1993 made it possible for healthcare professionals to get their first look at the qualitative data associated with hospitalization. This led to an improvement in the indicators that more accurately reflect the personal beliefs and experiences of patients. Many of these improved measures have been incorporated into the Hospital Consumer Assessment of Healthcare Providers and Systems (HCAHPS) survey over the course of time. This has led to the creation of domains that reflect nurse and physician communication, the responsiveness of hospital staff, the cleanliness and quietness of the hospital environment, pain

management, communication about medicines, discharge information, and an overall rating of the hospital as well as a hospital recommendation.[2] The HCAHPS survey is intended for distribution to patients after hospital discharge, which results in returned responses from patients with a variety of admitting diagnoses. The survey is a requirement for hospitals caring for patients funded by the Centers for Medicare & Medicaid Services, and the Centers for Medicare & Medicaid Services publishes findings for each hospital in relation to others in the same region and national scores on the Hospital Compare website. The HCAHPS survey was designed for distribution to patients after hospital discharge.[6] Patients hospitalized with acute stroke represent a very susceptible patient category with high rates of impairment upon discharge. [7–9] and major learning demands that encompass the pathogenesis of stroke as well as therapy, knowledge of personal stroke risk factors as well as their associated management, the ability to recognize stroke symptoms and warning signs. [10,11] The disability brought on by a stroke may reduce the number of people who respond to post-hospitalization surveys. The significant burden brought on by a stroke may also cause caregivers to respond more negatively to hospital quality surveys or not respond at all due to the increased caregiver burden once they are at home managing the reality of the disabilities brought on by the patient. [12–15] Additionally, research has shown that patient and family retention of learning related to stroke is poor at the time of hospital discharge. [11] Because of this, the HCAHPS survey items that focused on the provision of written educational materials during hospitalization and explanations about medications are likely to be poor surrogates for retained stroke knowledge. Stroke patients and their families may be an essential group of patients to investigate the hospitalization experience right before discharge. This is despite the fact that hospitals do not typically measure patient perceptions until after patients have been discharged from the facility. At a time when prompt response has come to be expected as the norm, healthcare professionals, for instance, might find it beneficial to have a knowledge of the experience of urgent diagnosis and treatment from the point of view of the patients and their families. In addition, it may be helpful to learn patient's and family member's actual knowledge of stroke warning signs and beliefs regarding how well they are prepared to assume responsibility for their own self-care after discharge. This information could be used to drive important changes in the way stroke discharge education is provided. As a result, one of our goals was to investigate the patient's and their significant other's lived experiences during the acute stroke hospitalization process and, ultimately, to build a quantitative instrument to capture this experience in an effort to promote rapid-cycle quality improvement.

Research Methodology

We conducted both qualitative and quantitative research in order to gain a better understanding of the perspectives held by patients and family members regarding the quality of acute stroke services.

Our procedure started with a qualitative exploration of the lived experience of hospitalization for patients with an acute stroke diagnosis and their family members. After that, we developed and serially refined a quantitative instrument for measurement of patient's and family's perceptions of the quality of acute stroke care.

The institutional review boards, both local and coordinating, gave their clearance to each stage of the study before it was carried out.

Qualitative Phase

During the qualitative portion of the research project, the major objective was to recognize key patient-derived themes that were regarded as being necessary for the delivery of high-quality acute stroke care. The patient and family experience of being hospitalized with an acute stroke event was investigated through the use of a focus group methodology in order to gain insight into patient and family views of markers of high-quality acute stroke hospital care. Ability to speak, read, and write; current hospitalization for a primary diagnosis of acute stroke; National Institutes of Health Stroke Scale (NIHSS) scores of 0 on items 1A, 1B, and 1C and a score of less than 1 on item 10; hemodynamically stable and physically capable of joining a focus group located within the hospital but outside the stroke unit. These were the requirements for patient eligibility for participation in a focus session. Eligibility requirements for the family

focus group included serving as a family spokesperson or next of kin for a patient who had a significant neurologic disability that rendered them incapable of speaking for themselves, as well as having more than three days of lived experience with the reference stroke admission.

The same person led each session of the focus group, and there were two people recording each one. Neither of these investigators was involved in the provision of patient or family care for any of the invited research participants. A convenience sample of acutely hospitalized stroke patients or family members of patients with a severe neurologic disability were recruited to participate in one of five focus groups over the course of a period of six months. There were two sessions that were reserved exclusively for families, two sessions that were reserved exclusively for patients, and one session that was reserved exclusively for both patients and families. All of the study participants gave their written consent, which was collected. Part I consisted of interviews using open-ended scripted questions, with all information simultaneously tape- and hand-recorded; part II consisted of completion of a brief questionnaire that asked patients and family members to rank, from most important to least important, a variety of hospital quality indicator categories derived from a review of existing hospitality measures and content expert consensus. All focus groups were conducted in two parts: part I consisted of interviews using open-ended scripted questions, with all information simultaneously tape- and hand-recorded.

Later on, the data from the scripted interviews that had been de-identified were transcribed verbatim from the tape recordings, and these transcriptions were complemented by notes that were recorded by the two hand-recorders. The interview data were subsequently coded and analyzed utilizing an inductive approach to thematic analysis. This was done to allow for the independence of theory and epistemology while simultaneously promoting the emergence of a detailed and complex account of the stroke hospitalization experience. Reading carefully was the initial phase in this procedure, and the goal was to locate meaningful text units that were pertinent to the subject of the investigation. Following this step, the sections of the text that discussed comparable topics were organized into analytic categories, and preliminary definitions were assigned to each category. Following this, the data were examined in a methodical manner to guarantee that a comprehensive collection of facts had been developed to support each category, and a descriptive name had been determined for each topic. To give further support for the importance of potential themes to acute stroke patients and their families, ranked hospital quality indicator categories from part II of the study were evaluated using descriptive statistics. These categories were taken from the study.

Quantitative Phase

The primary objective of the quantitative phase was to construct an instrument based on the findings of the qualitative phase and investigate its psychometric properties as well as its overall performance as a measure of patient and family perceptions of the quality of acute stroke care. This was accomplished through the use of the qualitative findings. The secondary objective of the study was to incorporate a participant knowledge test into the instrument. This test was derived from stroke center certification required stroke education elements [10,11] and its purpose was to investigate patient's and family's acquired knowledge in conjunction with their perceptions of the quality of the inpatient stroke education they were given.

Symmetric patient and family instruments were developed based on the domains identified in the qualitative phase of the study. These instruments were then serially refined by subject matter experts to a set of thirty survey items, twelve stroke knowledge test items, and five subject demographic fields. No identifying information was collected during this phase of the study. In order to convey the nature of the information gathered in the survey through the instrument, we gave it the name "STROKE (Stroke Treatment, Risk, Outcome Knowledge, Education) Perception Report." Items that were redundant with the HCAHPS survey were eliminated in order to allay fears regarding the filing of duplicate information. A benchmark reporting system was developed in order to evaluate the usefulness of comparing the responses of participating sites to an instrument that was developed in a manner analogous to that which is used by

existing commercial hospital quality instruments, with the exception that it was restricted solely to the findings of acute stroke patients or their families. The results of the surveys were classified according to the study location in order to facilitate the compilation of quarterly benchmark performance reporting and to support rapid-cycle program improvement activities.

Surveys were sent in their original sealed envelopes to the coordinating center, where they were input into SPSS (IBM version 23), cleaned by a researcher who was not linked with any study site, and then assessed by a psychometrician who was also independent. Using Cronbach's alpha, each scale was examined to determine its level of internal consistency and reliability; a score of 70 or more was regarded appropriate for a brand-new instrument. [16,17] To determine the extent to which the individual components of a scale measure the same underlying construct or factor, a construct validity test with exploratory factor analysis using principal components and varimax rotation was carried out. An excellent result was deemed to have a shared variance of fifty percent or more. [18,19] The data were evaluated descriptively for the entire sample, and tests of difference were performed to see whether or not the findings of patients and their families varied depending on factors such as race, age, education level, ethnicity, or length of time spent in the hospital. In order to provide a snapshot of site-specific patient and family responses, data from participating sites were analyzed in relation to data from other sites.[20-23] Following this analysis, the data were assembled into a report card that presented site aggregate findings alongside that of all other participating sites.

Result and Discussion

The population of the study was comprised of 139 consecutive individuals who presented themselves at Provincial Hospital, Janakpur, Nepal suffering from clinical stroke. Among these patients, 127 were given a head CT scan with no contrast, and 12 of them passed away before they could be given a CT scan. There were a total of 85 patients who were found to have either an acute or subacute stroke. 15 patients (10.8%) who presented with clinical stroke passed away while they were being treated at the hospital.

In terms of the patient population, there were patients residing in the different district. The 34% were engaged in farming for subsistence, 25% were owners of small businesses, 19% were working in housekeeping, and 22% were engaged in other types of work or were unemployed. Twenty patients had no formal education beyond elementary school, forty-five patients had only completed primary school, twelve patients had completed secondary school, and eight patients had completed college.

The head CT scan indicated that 77.6% of the patients had an ischemic stroke, while 22.4% of the patients had a hemorrhagic stroke. The average patient suffering from a stroke was 62.2 years old with an additional 16.2 years, and 51.8% of them were male. Age was a factor in an increase in the risk of having either an ischemic or a hemorrhagic stroke. The most common cause of ischemic stroke was atherosclerotic stroke, which was observed in 43.5% of patients who suffered from ischemic stroke. On the other hand, the most common cause of hemorrhagic stroke was intraparenchymal hemorrhage, which was observed in 78.9% of patients who suffered from hemorrhagic stroke. 39 patients were found to have symptoms that mimicked stroke, while 3 patients had repeat imaging that was normal. The results of the CT scans are shown in Table 1.

The results of the physical examination, the laboratory tests, and the ultrasound are listed in Table 2.

More than half of the patients who had either an ischemic or a hemorrhagic stroke reported having a history of hypertension, and more than half of the patients were found to have a blood pressure that was higher than 140/90 mm Hg. On the other hand, only 27 patients (or 32%) reported using anti-hypertensive drugs on an ad hoc basis, and only 7 patients (or 8%) reported using meds on a regular basis. Only three patients reported using aspirin on a consistent basis, and all three of them presented with symptoms of an ischemic stroke. It was revealed that 16 patients had a pulse that was irregularly irregular, although none of these patients had a history of atrial fibrillation or were using warfarin. However, all of these patients did have a pulse that was irregularly irregular. However, just 9 patients had a known

past diagnosis of diabetes despite the fact that 38 patients were found to have a fasting blood glucose level that was greater than 126 mg/dl, which is compatible with a diagnosis of diabetes mellitus. During the examination, atherosclerosis was determined to be present in the carotid arteries, and enlargement of the left ventricle of the heart was also observed. There were a total of 2 patients whose syphilis serology was confirmed to be reactive.

Table 1: Non-contrast head CT scan findings among all patients

Non-contrast head CT scan finding	N (%)
Ischemic Stroke	66 (52.0)
Hemorrhagic Stroke	19 (15.0)
*Neoplasm	8 (6.3)
Severe brain atrophy	8 (6.3)
*Subdural hematoma	6 (4.7)
*Brain abscess	4 (3.1)
Toxoplasmosis	4 (3.1)
Normal repeated CT scan on day 7	3(2.4)
Intracranial hypertension	3(2.4)
Extensive calcifications	2(1.6)
Pan-sinusitis	1(0.8)
Meningoencephalitis	1(0.8)
Tuberculosis choroiditis	1(0.8)
*Chronic epidural hematoma	1(0.8)

Table 2: Physical examination, laboratory and ultrasound studies of common stroke risk factors

	Stroke subtype	
	Ischemic	Hemorrhagic
Past Medical History		
Hypertension	57.6	68.4
Physical inactivity	40.9	36.8
Diabetes mellitus	12.1	5.2
Current Smoking	7.6	5.2
Alcohol	18.2	21.1
Examination findings		
Irregularly irregular pulse	22.7	5.3
Syst >140mmHg	47.0	73.7
Diast >90mmHg	36.4	68.4
Laboratory findings		
Total cholesterol >200mg/dl	31.0	39.0
LDL cholesterol >110mg/dl	43.1	33.3
HDL cholesterol <40mg/dl	38.0	17.0
Triglycerides >150mg/dl	23.1	33.3
FBS >126mg/dl	43.1	55.6
Reactive TPPA	26.2	50.0
Reactive HIV serology	7.7	0
Ultrasound findings		

Fig. 3. Proportional breakdown of time from symptom onset to hospital arrival (median).

Fig. 4. Breakdown of the timeline of symptom onset to hospital arrival by type of presentation and mode of transport (median (IQR))

Type of presentation	Mode of transport (hours: minutes)	Symptom onset to hospital arrival (hours)
GP referral (20%)	Private transport	48 (18-120)
Primary EMS (31%)	Call to hospital arrival: 1:31 (1:03-2:40)	18 (6.5-48)
Self-referral (29%)	Private transport	24 (12-72)
Clinic referral (19%)	Private transport (13%)	132 (48-168)
	EMS (87%); Call to hospital arrival: 2:27 (1:04-4:37)	16 (10-48)

The approaches that are linked with qualitative and survey research both contribute to the work's inherent limits. These constraints definitely exist. To begin, it is quite possible that other significant dimensions exist that are connected with the experience of hospitalization following the admission of a patient suffering from acute stroke. Our focus groups were comprised of a relatively small number of stroke patients and family members, which is typical of qualitative research. As a result, the findings of our participants might not be an accurate representation of the beliefs held by all stroke patients. Nevertheless, we took care not to steer our qualitative subjects in any particular direction, and despite this, each group articulated compelling experiences and beliefs that are comparable to those expressed by the other groups. Second, we have to operate under the assumption that the opinions and responses to the knowledge test are given in an honest manner by the individuals who take part in the survey. This is something that is required in all survey research. The fact that our findings were able to load consistently across both patients and family members is symbolic of the validity of the work that we did, and the instrument's support is further bolstered by the fact that it has very reasonable dependability.

Conclusions

The STROKE Perception Report provides stroke center staff with the ability to understand patients' and family members' beliefs regarding the quality of acute stroke care in three essential new domains that have never been explored before. These domains are crucial to the responsibilities of vascular neurologists and nurses who work in this fast-paced and rapidly evolving specialty. Stroke center hospitals are in a good position to enhance and celebrate the treatment they provide in support of this vulnerable patient population if they grasp these critical perspectives of acute stroke services as seen through the eyes of stroke survivors and caregivers.

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